

Literature review

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Problem statement, why is pre-mobility preparation and post-mobility intervention important?

Extensive literature confirms the diverse benefits of studying abroad. Internationally mobile students enjoy several benefits, including the development of language competence and skills relevant to their field of study, improved employment prospects and career advancement, heightened global awareness and intercultural competence, and personal growth overall (Goldstein, 2022a; Nerlich, 2020). For host countries, the advantages include financial gains, cultural enrichment, and the acquisition of knowledge and diverse perspectives (Smith & Khawaja, 2011). Sending countries benefit from an expanded labor force equipped with enhanced skills across various domains, contributing to national economic prosperity (Nerlich, 2020). Goldstein, however, in her comprehensive review on intercultural learning through study abroad (2022a), emphasized a widespread agreement among both researchers and practitioners regarding the necessity of pre-mobility preparation as well as post-mobility programs for students.

An essential inquiry concerns the correlation between study abroad experiences and the advancement of intercultural competence. On a cautionary note, relying on previous empirical works in literature, Skrefsrud (2021) calls attention to the possibility of student mobility programs leading to unintended consequences such as the superficial understanding of the cultural and social context of host society, the „objectifying tourist gaze”, strengthened cultural stereotypes and ethnocentric views. He argues that if student mobility is to be successful, there is a need for „developing targeted support for pre- and post-mobility that enhances students’ understanding of intercultural learning. „ (p.72). He simultaneously advocates for a transcultural approach that views cultural identities as relational, dynamic, and transformative, rather than categorically determined. His conceptualization of culture is similar to the non-essentialist view of culture of Holliday (2013). He argues against a mechanistic, static, categorical approach to culture, which leads to conceptualizations of intercultural learning "as a means of deciphering cultural codes that make the message in the interaction process understandable" (p.66), probably via rather simplified culture-specific contents. Similarly, Bhawuk (2017), a long-time intercultural training expert posits that by initially acquiring fundamental knowledge and culture-general skills (e.g. in pre-departure culture-general training), expatriates can enhance their capacity to integrate culture-specific knowledge and skills on-site while residing in a different cultural environment. In PADMICA, we will apply a culture-general instead of culture-specific approach.

In their influential study, Vande Berg and colleagues (2012) argued that mere intercultural interaction—simply the encounter between internationally mobile students and individuals from diverse cultures in a new environment—might not inherently lead to the development of intercultural competence. They advocate for

the necessity of „intentional and deliberate pedagogical approaches, activated throughout the study abroad cycle (before, during, and after), that are designed to enhance students' intercultural competence.” (Paige&Vande Berg, 2012, pp. 29-30.) In PADMICA, we adopt this framework to describe interventions both before (preparation module) and after (debriefing module) mobility.

Research regarding how the study-abroad experience itself could enhance intercultural learning or intercultural competence faces several methodological limitations, therefore compromising the generalibility of findings (Goldstein, 2022a). One of these limitations is the overreliance on self-reports, just like in any other social science research. Students might overreport their intercultural competence when asked, this is the well-known manifestation of social desirability or the motive to maintain a positive face. On the other hand, the essence of the deficiency or weakness in intercultural sensitivity lies in the unawareness of this state. As students progress in their intercultural competence during their study abroad experiences, they become more conscious of and recognize to a greater degree their own intercultural inadequacies. This phenomenon, known as the intercultural learning paradox, can result in inconclusive findings in studies examining the impact of study abroad on the development of intercultural competence, particularly when relying solely on self-reports from students (Goldstein, 2022b). Furthermore, not all the aspects of intercultural competence are equally accessible for individuals in questions, therefore they are not capable of giving a full self-report.

Intercultural learning interventions both before and after studying abroad can assist students in recognizing and consciously reflecting on their cultural assumptions, many of which they may be unaware of. This initial step is considered a prerequisite for successful interaction and collaboration with individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds.(Cohen-Emerique, 2013; Jones, Miles & Gopalkrishnan, 2019; Sue et al., 2019).

Preparation before and debriefing sessions after the study abroad experience are considered crucial because the relatively short duration of the mobility limits students' processing of intercultural experiences. Preparation can also help improve the alignment between predeparture expectations and the actual experiences of the sojourn. The gap between them is a significant contributor to stress reported by international students (Pitts, 2009). Both students before their departure and various preparation programs tend to focus more on anticipated external challenges such as language barriers, logistical issues, and practical considerations, rather than internal factors such as identity, stress management, intercultural competence, ethnocentrism, and cultural values. (Goldstein&Keller, 2015; Jones, Schartner&Young, 2016; Pilon, 2017).

To conclude this section, we can refer to Bathurst and La Brack who summarized their experiences as follows: „...We gradually came to understand that the primary intercultural learning from study abroad did not necessarily occur abroad, but rather as a result of particular kinds of reflection on the experience abroad—and that the frequency and depth of those reflections could be increased by structured interventions both before and after the study abroad experience.” (Bathurst & La Brack, 2012, p. 268.)

Chapter 2 Acculturation and cross-cultural adaptation of international students

To effectively design and implement pre-mobility and post-mobility intervention programs to enhance intercultural learning for international students, it is essential to gain a deep understanding of the processes of mobility and what factors influence its outcomes. In this endeavour, we can build on the extensive knowledge body accumulated in the acculturation and cross-cultural adaptation, especially those of international students (Alharbi & Smith, 2018; Berry, 2019; Smith & Khawaja, 2011).

As described in the literature (Berry, 2019), acculturation refers to the cultural and psychological changes resulting from encounters between individuals and groups with different cultural backgrounds.

The acculturation literature of the past decades has been dominated by John W. Berry's acculturation model (Berry, 1997, 2003, 2019; Berry and Sam, 2016), which takes as its starting point a theoretical framework of the components of acculturation and the relationship between them (see Figure 1.). In this model, two cultures – that of the ethnocultural group one belongs to, e.g. an international student from Hungary, and that of the larger society, e.g. the host society in the Netherlands where the student studies – are included, and contact between them can result in cultural, linguistic, religious, physical, biological, economic, and social changes in both cultures. In addition to these cultural/group level phenomena, the theoretical framework addresses psychological/individual level acculturation (behavioral changes, acculturation stress, acculturation strategies) and their adaptation (psychological, socio-cultural and intercultural) to the new situation. Psychological/individual factors are at the forefront of psychological research.

Figure 1. Berry's framework for conceptualizing and studying acculturation (2019)

As regards the way in which people from different cultures come into contact with each other, it is worth considering the well-known systems of cultural dimensions (e.g. Hofstede, 2001; Triandis, 1994, 1996). The first and best known (and often heavily criticised, e.g. see Skrefsrud in a previous section of this text) system of cultural dimensions, based on large-scale empirical research, is that of Hofstede. The following cultural dimensions are listed by Hofstede: (1) Power distance: to what extent do members of the culture accept that power is unequally distributed in different institutions and organizations, how respectfully one should address supervisors, professors and so on. (2) Uncertainty avoidance: to what extent do members of the culture feel uncomfortable in uncertain, unstructured and ambiguous situations - this leads them to cope with life's uncertainties by planning and focusing on stability. (3) Individualism and its opposite pole, collectivism: the focus is on the individual person or on the group? Individuals must provide for themselves and their immediate family, or expect care from their own group in return for loyalty. (4) Masculinity and its counterpart, femininity: relative emphasis on achievement, self-actualization, material success, or, in contrast, on relationships, modesty, quality of life. (5) A fifth dimension, long vs. short-term orientation, emerged in a later, extensive analysis. This dimension indicates the extent to which members of the culture accept the delayed satisfaction of material, social and emotional needs (Hofstede, 1991). More recently, a sixth dimension of indulgence versus self restraint has been suggested. Indulgence represents a society where basic and natural human desires for enjoyment and fun are freely gratified, while restraint characterizes a society that tightly regulates such gratification through strict social norms.

The definitions of individualism and collectivism that have been more widely used in the literature are those proposed by Oyserman and colleagues (2002), based on the work of Triandis (1995): individualism is understood as the valuation of independence and individuality, while collectivism is understood as the valuation of duty to one's group and of harmony. It was also Triandis who introduced the

tight-loose culture dimension into cultural psychology research (1994, 1996), for which a systematic, multi-country study was conducted (Gelfand et al., 2011). In tight cultures, rules and norms are more strict and clearly prescribed, with more severe sanctions for violations.

According to Berry's model (see Figure 2.), we can talk about different acculturation strategies (in other words, cultural orientations) according to (1) the relation to the ethnocultural group and (2) the relation to the larger (host) society. Depending on whether the individual has a positive or negative attitude towards the traditions of the ethnocultural group, the maintenance of their identity on the one hand and the search for contact with the host/mainstream society and its various groups on the other hand, we can distinguish four possible strategies: integration (both maintaining one's original culture and seeking relationships with other groups), separation (maintaining original culture but avoiding interactions with other groups), assimilation (not holding on to their culture of origin but seeking relationships with other groups) or marginalization (lack of both). In line with these four strategies of the ethnocultural groups, the expectations of the larger (host) society regarding the acculturation of different ethnocultural groups can also be of four types: multiculturalism, segregation, melting pot and exclusion.

Figure 2. Acculturation strategies in ethnocultural groups and the larger society (Berry, 2019)

A large amount of research work has shown that the integration strategy occurs most often and has the most positive outcomes (see Berry et al's 2006 study of more than 7,000 adolescents in 13 countries; Nguyen and Benet-Martínez's meta-analysis 2013). Despite the fact that these studies and others consistent with their findings are widely cited in the literature, Rudmin (2016) and Bierwiazzonek & Kunst (2021) have voiced methodological and other criticisms and consider the seemingly

undivided optimism about the absolute benefits of the integration strategy to be unfounded. In the case of international students, several studies have shown that orientation towards the host culture is indeed positively related to mental health, while orientation towards the culture of origin is negatively related (e.g. Taušová et al., 2019). Similar results were found in Demes and Geeraert's (2014) study of international students and other sojourner groups, in which individuals who were subject to an assimilation strategy had the best adaptation indicators. This strategy is probably 'obvious' because of its transience, while students are aware that their culture of origin will endure and that they will eventually return to it, adaptation to the host culture is consequently hindered by a 'reinforcing' attachment to their culture of origin, as evidenced by frequent daydreaming or 'chronic homesickness'.

It is becoming increasingly difficult to identify which is the majority, inclusive social 'mainstream' group with which a member of the ethnocultural group seeks or less seeks contact (Berry and Sam, 2016; van Oudenhoven and Benet-Martínez, 2015; van Oudenhoven and Ward, 2013). Berry and Sam suggest that it is therefore worth examining contact between not just two but several groups. In the case of acculturation of international students, for example, the community of other international students may constitute one of the most important such groups. Thus, not only the orientation towards the culture of origin and the host culture, but also the orientation towards the community of international students should be taken into account, putting an additional dimension to the investigation (Taušová et al., 2019). It is also important to explore the patterns of relationships and contacts that exist (or do not exist) between international student groups. These patterns of connections are probably not independent of the relative status of the origin groups. Indeed, power relations and status play a prominent role in contact. It is rare for two groups with completely equal power positions to meet (Berry and Sam, 2016). Their relative status, their perceived economic, political, linguistic power and ethnolinguistic vitality - "a group's ability to maintain and protect its existence in time as a collective entity with a distinctive identity and language" (Giles, Taylor and Bourhis, 1977, p. 308) may be important factors.

Ward is credited with the distinction between two main types of adaptation, psychological adaptation and sociocultural adaptation (Searle and Ward, 1990; Ward, 2001). The former is based on affective responses, refers to the individual's feelings, well-being, satisfaction, and fits into the themes of stress and coping. The latter is based on behavioural responses, relates to the individual's ability to 'fit in' and interact effectively, and theoretically belongs more to the domain of cultural learning (Masgoret and Ward, 2006). More recently, Berry and Sam (2016) have introduced a third type of intercultural adaptation. This type of adaptation describes the extent to which an individual manages to develop harmonious and positive intercultural relationships and avoid negative stereotyping and discriminatory behavior. Berry has given an interpretation that is readily applicable to everyday language, according to which psychological adaptation is about

"feeling well", while sociocultural adaptation is „doing well” and intercultural adaptation is „relating well” (Berry, 2019). In the case of international students, academic adaptation (doing well at school and navigating well the new educational system) is also essential.

Schartner and Young (2016) have suggested an integrative theoretical model that encompasses the whole cycle of the experience of international students, starting from pre-sojourn (cultural and language knowledge of host society, previous intercultural experiences, motivation, intercultural competence) via during sojourn (social interactions with locals and international students, and social support...) to post-sojourn, the contributory factors to the process of cross-cultural transition (adjustment) and the outcomes of that process (adaptation).

Expanding Ward's well-known ABC model of acculturation (Ward, 2001), where A stands for the affective processes (stress and coping, focusing on the emotional responses to cross-cultural transition); B stands for behavioral component, referring to culture learning, centering around the acquisition of new skills and appropriate behaviors; C stands for cognitive element, with the focus on identity, self- and ingroup perception and the perception of other groups, cultural orientations and intercultural relations, in 2019, Ward and Szabó has added developmental processes (D) to the alphabet of acculturation (Ward & Szabó, 2019). This addition addresses an important issue, the inherent connection between acculturation and development, including the personal as well as cultural identity development and the learning process of cultural orientations. We could further argue that many students pursuing study abroad are in the age of emerging adulthood, proposed by Arnett (2015) as a new life stage between adolescence and young adulthood between the ages of 18 and 29. Arnett considers this as a new phenomenon in the last decades in affluent countries. This stage of life is characterized as the age of identity explorations during which young people encounter instability due to changes in various domains. It is also a self-focused and independent age due to the relatively low number of daily role obligations. The feeling of in-between, the feeling of neither adolescent nor adult can also be strong, but at the same time, this is the age of several opportunities and the pressure of choices.

The rich literature on the acculturation and adaptation of international students (e.g. Alharbi & Smith, 2018; Demes & Geeraert, 2014; Geeraert et al., 2022; Smith & Khawaja, 2011; Taušová et al., 2019) has addressed a plethora of significant factors. We will list these factors briefly in a working model (Figure 3.) in which the acculturation strategies or cultural orientations and the different types of adaptation mentioned above are also to be found.

Figure 3. Working model of acculturation and adaptation of international students

Cultural distance: the perceived distance between the culture of origin and host culture

Demes et Geeraert (2014) pointed to the relationship between perceived cultural distance – in language, friendship, people's attitudes, values, norms, family life, food and eating, daily practices, living standards, social environment, natural environment, climate - and psychological and sociocultural adaptation. Large perceived cultural distance is associated with poorer adaptation, more stress, anxiety, low self-esteem and lower levels of life satisfaction. Similarly, Taušová and colleagues (2019) found a positive relationship between cultural distance and acculturation stress, namely that perceptions of cultural distance influence acculturation stress through (weaker) orientation towards the host culture. If international students have positive feelings about the perceived cultural difference between the educational system in the host compared to the country of origin, it can lead to positive academic adaptation (Nguyen Luu, 2019).

Motivations and goals for studying abroad

Chirkov et al. (2007, 2008) found that adaptation success is predicted primarily by self-regulation and autonomous motivation, i.e. intrinsic motivation and personal commitment to and identification with the importance of studying abroad. In contrast, extrinsic regulation and introjected motivation, where the individual feels an inner drive to conform to the expectations of others, are less decisive. A classic study, noted by Boneva and Frieze (2001), based on a comparison between students who prefer to study abroad and those who prefer to stay at home, found that while achievement and power motivation were stronger in those who chose mobility, affiliation (connection to significant others) motivation was stronger in those who chose to stay at home.

Identity and identity change

International students are exposed to studying abroad in the midst of their identity formation (see emerging adulthood above). However, identity change among international students is an under-researched area in the literature (Zhang & Goodson, 2011). Benet-Martínez (2012) depicts the attempt to integrate two identities (e.g. those of origin and host country) in acculturating individuals along two dimensions: (1) the extent to which the two identities overlap, are blended or compartmentalized, and (2) the extent to which the relationship between the two identities is harmonious or conflictual. Those for whom the two identities are well integrated (blended and harmonious with one another) have a range of advantages, from cognitive complexity to creativity to cultural openness.

The Cultural Identity Model of the Cultural Transition Cycle, (Sussman, 2000, 2002) describes the different stages of identity change during a sojourn that results in either subtractive identity, when the individual feels less strongly rooted in their identity of origin, or additive identity, when the individual adds new elements from the host culture to their identity. Findings of an interview research with more than 100 international students in Hungary and Hungarian students studying in different countries (Nguyen Luu, 2019) have shown, however, a richer repertoire of identity and identity change, ranging from maintaining ethnocultural identity and the change in religious identity via multilevel identities such as international/global identity, continental (e.g. Asian) or regional (Eastern European) and identification with the place of study to identity threat due to discrimination.

Personality

van der Zee and Van Oudenhoven's (2000) Multicultural Personality Questionnaire conceptualizes and measures five personality dimensions, namely: cultural empathy, open-mindedness, social initiative, emotional stability, and flexibility. These five dimensions have been found to be closely related to international students' adaptation (Leong, 2007; van Oudenhoven and van der Zee, 2002). Smith and Khawaja (2011) highlighted the positive impact of a number of personality factors on the creation of new friendships and, through this, on psychological and sociocultural adaptation. These personality traits include secure attachment styles, low trait-level anxiety and extraversion. Research has also shown that maladaptive perfectionism, i.e. unrealistic expectations of one's own performance, especially when associated with acculturation stress, is a strong predictor of depression among international students (Hamamura and Laird, 2014; Huang and Mussap, 2018). Research by Geeraert and colleagues (2019), following a so-called interactionist perspective, showed that international students studying in tighter cultures (where rules and norms are more strict and clearly prescribed, with more severe sanctions for violations) have poorer adaptation than students studying in looser cultures. However, the personality traits of the students mitigate the

difficulties encountered in tight cultures: international students with the qualities of honesty-humility and loving-kindness do well in such environments.

Culture shock, acculturation and academic stress

The concept of culture shock, introduced by the anthropologist Oberg (1960), has now entered the professional and public discourse. This phenomenon describes the experiences of disorientation, anxiety and confusion lived by newcomers in an unfamiliar cultural environment. Several models have been developed to describe the evolution of these over time, perhaps the best known of which describes change along the inverted U curve (Figure 4.). The history of this model began with Lysgaard's 1955 study of the American experience of Scandinavian Fulbright scholars. The excitement and joy experienced on arrival (the 'honeymoon phase' in the model's description, when stress levels are still low) is followed by the confrontation with differences and difficulties and the resulting high level of stress and culture shock. This process is illustrated by the ascending branch of the inverted U curve. Over time, people learn to cope with a lot of stress and become in a better state of mind thanks to the exposure to new environments and culture learning. This is indicated by the descending branch of the inverted U curve that leads to the stage of mastery, the effective functioning in the new culture.

Figure 4. The inverted U curve of culture shock

Gullahorn and Gullahorn (1963) extended the inverted U curve to the inverted W curve (i.e., double inverted U curve), which also included a shock on return.

Research findings have been, however, inconclusive in terms of U and W curves. For example, in a study of 2500 exchange students from 50 different countries, Demes and Geeraert found a total of five typical patterns in the stress levels of the participating students that are explained by different personality, coping and adaptation variables. Their findings show that the U curve was only one among 5 typical patterns.

The term acculturation stress, with a more positive connotation, as proposed by Berry (2005), is increasingly gaining ground in the literature, instead of the more sonorous culture shock, with the possibility of drawing on the rich theoretical framework of stress-coping psychology and its related research tradition.

In moving and adapting to a new environment and culture, the international student encounters a myriad of stressors. Among the predictors of psychological adaptation, stress ranks at the top (Zhang and Goodson 2011). A large amount of research also confirms this trend (e.g. Bai, 2016; Alharbi & Smith, 2018): acculturation stress predicts poor mental health and low levels of psychological well-being.

In addition to acculturation stress, students must also cope with studies- and school-related stress or academic stress. In their widely cited review study, Smith and Khawaja (2011) highlight that, compared to local students, for most international students, besides the difficulty posed by the foreign language, navigating the new educational system can also be problematic, and the stress experienced in the academic world significantly affects overall stress levels and psychological distress. Additionally, discrepancies between performance-related expectations - both personal and familial, or even sponsor-related - and actual achievements are also significant sources of stress.

Rienties and Tempelaar (2013) found significant differences in academic and social adaptation among international students studying at nine different universities in the Netherlands. In cultures with high power distance, individuals of lower status typically show respect towards those higher in the hierarchy and accept the unequal distribution of power within organizations and society in general. According to the study, students from these cultures exhibited poorer adaptation indicators. The authors suggest that students accustomed to teacher-centered education from such cultures may struggle with student-centered, problem-, project-, and competency-based Dutch education, where active student participation is key to success. Particularly, students from Confucian background countries (such as China, Taiwan, Vietnam) faced challenges at the studied Dutch universities.

Students from different educational systems often enter the classroom with varying - often implicit - expectations, such as the roles of teachers and students, or the natural proximity (e.g., friendliness) and power distance between teachers and students (Brok & Koopman, 2007).

Reentry

Several studies refer to the experience of return shock among international students. Dettweiler et al. (2015), examining the experiences of German students returning home after 5 months of study abroad, 8 months after their arrival, found an inverted U-curve. Contrary to the literature to date, which tends to focus on negative return experiences (problematic, shocking, difficult, painful, bereavement, traumatic) and mental health problems (anxiety, loneliness, isolation, frustration, apathy, anger, hostility, helplessness, even depression), Kartoshkina (2015), interviewing US students returning to their old university, prefers the adjective "bitter-sweet", a mix of positive and negative experiences. On the „sweet” side is the encounter with all the things they missed: important people, home, their own culture. Another positive experience is the contact with people with similar experiences (also returning), sharing experiences with them and, last but not least, (re)appreciating things at home. On the "bitter" side, there is the loss of all the contacts and things they had and learned abroad, the criticism of their own country and the difficulty of not being able to tell what they have experienced during their period of study abroad, without finding an audience.

Pritchard (2011) interviewed masters students who had returned from a university in Northern Ireland to Sri Lanka and Taiwan. The results of her study showed that the inverted W curve in emotion was not confirmed by the experiences of the majority of students. They reported that they had not experienced any return trauma or emotional difficulties in relationships with family and close friends. They were also able to re-engage with their wider social network relatively easily. They experienced difficulties or "return trauma" more in the areas of collectivism-individualism, and tradition-modernity. To give an example, a woman returning home with a highly prestigious degree is again and still perceived by her husband and family as inferior. Bochner (2006) listed gender role perceptions, attitudes towards superiors and alcohol consumption as possible sources of difficulties for returning students. We might add that this is more relevant for international students returning from the (more liberal) West to more traditional cultures. For students returning from Malaysia to Germany, however, the experience is different.

Presbitero's research (2016) suggests that cultural intelligence (CQ) – the capability of an individual to operate proficiently in environments marked by cultural diversity – helps reduce the harmful impacts of both culture shock (while in the host country) and reverse culture shock (upon returning home) on international students' psychological and sociocultural adjustment. This study too, calls attention to the importance of developing intercultural competence of international students both before and after their mobility.

After reviewing various theoretical frameworks on reentry (e.g., Szkudlarek, 2010; Sussman, 2002) and conceptualizing reentry as an ongoing, interactive, and

interconnected aspect of cultural transition which is a natural part of acculturation, Chi and Martin (2020) propose the Integrated Network Theory of Reentry. Using a relational and network approach, this theory posits that social networks, influenced by communication, play a pivotal role in cultural transitions. It provides a framework for research and post-reentry programs, addressing three fundamental questions: (1) What are the defining characteristics of reentry social networks? (2) How do specific mechanisms shape the structure of returning individuals' social networks? (3) What impacts do these social networks have on the reentry experience? As recommendations for post-mobility intervention, the authors suggest that a comprehensive training program that includes key players in the social networks of the returnees (and not only the returnees themselves) could be more effective and efficient. Furthermore, with readily available network data collection and visualization software, network visualization can be used as a tool to address trainees' network situation and issues in an informal and engaging manner. This can help clearly illustrate to returning students the potential causes of their feelings of depression, homesickness, or alienation and help trainees in devising effective network strategies aimed at making the most of their social connections.

As far as measurements of different factors of reentry process are concerned, Tomlin et al. (2014) provide a full set of various surveys and items. These are survey questions regarding preparedness for reverse culture shock, symptoms of reverse culture shock, survey questions regarding available support networks, a survey question regarding who students mostly talked to for support, or survey questions regarding participation in re-entry sessions/workshops. These are available in their study in a full-text form and could be used for the Debriefing module.

Discrimination

Nilsson et al's (2008) study found that discrimination is the only factor that leads to differences in the levels of acculturation stress experienced by different groups of international students. Montreuil and Bourhis (2001) were the first to formulate the idea that majority society discriminates between different minority groups by considering some groups as 'valued' and others as 'devalued'. Alharbi and Smith (2018) and Akhtar and Kröner-Herwig (2015) posit that among international students, those from Asia, Africa and Latin America experience greater acculturation stress than students from any European country, not independently from the exposure to discrimination. Wei et al. (2008) demonstrated that perceived discrimination influences depression levels regardless of the general stress perceived by students. Experiencing discrimination correlates with elevated stress levels solely when individuals utilize less adaptive coping mechanisms (e.g., repression) and possess low self-esteem.

Nguyen Luu's (2019) findings, derived from interviews with international students in Hungary, identified two distinct forms of discrimination: firstly, discrimination based on being a foreigner, predominantly encountered by European students;

and secondly, discrimination rooted in belonging to a particular ethnic or national group, primarily experienced by students from the global South.

Tan and Liu's (2014) research findings show that compared to other international students, "visible" minority students have a stronger acculturation orientation towards the group of origin and a weaker orientation towards the host culture. Meanwhile, there is a negative correlation between the latter acculturation orientation and the discrimination they expect to face. The results also show that for them, discrimination, and not perceived cultural distance, will determine acculturation orientation.

Loneliness and homesickness

Lack of belonging, loneliness and homesickness are also major sources of stress for students studying abroad. Sawir and colleagues (2008) distinguish between different types of loneliness experienced in this situation: personal loneliness (due to the absence of family), social loneliness (due to the absence of a network of relationships), and cultural loneliness (due to the absence of a familiar and popular cultural and linguistic environment). Homesickness and the longing for a familiar environment, is associated with sadness, loneliness, maladjustment and less effective learning, according to a study by Poyrazli and Lopez (2007). The authors found that young students from non-European countries, with poorer English language skills and more likely to have experienced discrimination, report stronger homesickness. Constant and intensive communication with parents back home can, however, have negative consequences, as students miss out on enjoyable social bonding activities and experience higher levels of acculturation stress (Messina, 2007). Homesickness has a negative impact on sociocultural adaptation but can be partly relieved by Facebook interactions and other online social connections. Especially Facebook interactions with host-country network can lower homesickness (Billedo, Kerkhof & Finkenauer, 2020).

Coping

International students can mobilise a variety of resources to cope with the many challenges, difficulties and stressors they face. Smith and Khawaja (2011), however, summarise that there is little research highlighting positive coping strategies for international students, despite the fact that almost all major acculturation theory models emphasise the importance of coping. Szabó, Ward, and Jose (2016) conducted a longitudinal study exploring the relationship between uprooting, coping strategies, and anxiety among international students in New Zealand. They found that separation stress heightens anxiety, particularly when primary control coping mechanisms are employed to change the situation, whereas secondary coping strategies, such as acceptance and positive reinterpretation, lessen separation distress. This suggests that in situations beyond the students' control, primary coping is less effective.

A decorative circular graphic on the left side of the page, consisting of several overlapping, semi-transparent colored segments in shades of blue, green, yellow, and red, matching the PADMICA logo.

While repressive coping style predicts negative psychological well-being, reflective style is associated with positive psychological well-being in all the three groups of Asian, European and Latin-American international student groups in a study by Akhtar & Kröner-Herwig (2019). The study also found typical significant differences between these groups. Students from Asia showed a higher level of suppressive coping compared to the other groups, mirroring the Asian value of emotional self-control and expressive suppression. Students from Latin America had a higher level of reflective coping as compared to Asian and European students.

Language

It's obvious, that linguistic competence influences all elements of the teaching and learning process. For international students participating in EMI (English-medium Instruction) English language proficiency is also a predictor of both psychological and sociocultural adaptation (Zhang & Goodson, 2011). Drawing on a number of studies, Smith and Khawaja (2011) also highlighted the strong link between language proficiency and academic success, making friends and having relationships with locals, and seeking support when needed. Low language skills and acculturation stress and depression go hand in hand (Duru and Poyrazli, 2007; Yeh and Inose, 2003).

The dominating role of the English language - see linguistic imperialism (by the English language, Phillipson, 1997) or native speakerism (Holliday, 2006), which emphasizes the superiority of native speakers, especially in the case of English – also contributes to the formation of hierarchy among international students based on their English competence. If the local language is different from the language of instruction at the university, international students can end up in an international bubble, more separated from locals, and can also face double language barriers (both in the local language and the English language of instruction, both their own language barriers and those of the locals (Nguyen Luu, 2019).

Social relationships

All the main theoretical models of acculturation emphasize the role of peer relationships and peer support in mental health. Stress and peer support were found to be the most significant predictors of psychological adaptation (Zhang and Goodson, 2011). Relationships with locals were the most important predictors of sociocultural adaptation. Of particular note is the 2011 research by Hendrickson, Rosen, and Aune, which highlights the importance of the three social relationships - social relationships with co-nationals, international students from other countries, and friendships with locals. More recent research shows that those who socialized with both co-national peers and locals or internationals and locals reported more positive wellbeing outcomes (Szabó, Z.Papp & Nguyen Luu, 2020).

Not only the presence, or the quantity of intergroup contacts counts. Mak, Brown and Wadey (2014) found that high levels of quality intergroup contact, low levels of intergroup anxiety and high levels of positive intercultural communication emotions predict positive attitudes of local and international students towards each other. Although the contact and meaningful interaction with locals could have a highly positive impact on their adaptation outcomes, it often remains an unfulfilled desire of several international students (Williams and Johnson, 2011).

Institutional support also significantly influences the psychological well-being, satisfaction with university life, and reduces stress levels of international students. Identification with the university correlates with perceptions of support and satisfaction derived from it (Cho and Yu, 2015).

In this chapter, we have attempted to give an overview of the literature on the acculturation and adaptation of international students. We have taken into account numerous factors that influence the outcome of mobility. The list is naturally incomplete, important factors such as gender and the use of computer-mediated-communication was not included. The final element on our introduced list is intercultural competence. We dedicate the entire Chapter 3 to elaborate on in detail.

Chapter 3 Intercultural competence

With this chapter, we aim to introduce essential components from the literature on intercultural competence necessary for a project designed to promote intercultural learning and develop intercultural competence for international students during both the pre-mobility and post-mobility stages of their study abroad.

What is intercultural competence?

Rathje (2007) quotes the social psychologist Gardner's question „...to what degree is it actually possible, for an expert from one culture to communicate with, to get through to, persons of another culture?“ and answer in 1962: „ [intercultural competence is] unusual capacity with personality traits such as integrity, stability, extroversion, socialisation in universal values, special intuitive and telepathic abilities.“

The research and application of intercultural competence has come a long way since then. It's now widely acknowledged that acquiring intercultural competence doesn't require innate or extraordinary abilities like telepathy. Instead, there's a general consensus that intercultural competence can be developed through learning and experience, particularly through dedicated programs aimed at enhancing it deliberately.

In both PADMICA and this literature review, we consistently employ the term "intercultural competence" among a diverse array of related concepts. Some of

these include cross-cultural adaptation, cross-cultural effectiveness, cultural competence, cultural intelligence, cultural proficiency, global citizenship, global competence, global learning, international mindedness, intercultural sensitivity, intercultural skills, and multicultural competence.

„Intercultural competence is broadly defined as communication and behavior that are both effective and appropriate in intercultural interactions, with effectiveness referring to the degree to which the individual's goals are achieved and appropriateness referring to the manner and context in which those goals are achieved.” (Deardorff, 2015, p. 218). The interactions mentioned in this well-known definition take place „...between people who, to some degree or another, represent different or divergent affective, cognitive, and behavioral orientations to the world.” (Spitzberg & Chagnon 2009, p.7).

Components of intercultural competence

There is a plethora of definitions, approaches of intercultural competence. Rather widely agreed-on lists of vital knowledge areas, essential skills, and significant attitudes of intercultural competence can be found in the frameworks of intercultural competence as follows : (Deardorff, 2015)

Knowledge

Cultural self-knowledge and awareness,

Knowledge of other cultures,

Knowledge of other languages (including sociolinguistic knowledge),

Contextual knowledge (historical, literary, and cultural elements, alongside political, economic, and religious systems shaping society).

Skills

Listening/attentiveness (to the explicit as well as to the implicit elements of the interaction),

Observing thoughtfully (including the nonverbal cues and oneself),

Reflecting or mindfulness (selfmonitoring/self attending and critical self-reflection),

Perspective taking (being aware of and able to take others' perspectives),

Communicating, verbal and nonverbal communication, (including awareness of individual and cultural communication styles, and the ability to adapt as needed in intercultural interactions),

Language skills could be added but being fluent in a language alone does not ensure efficient and appropriate interaction.

Attitudes

Open-mindedness (suspending judgment or assumptions),

Curiosity (desire to learn about others and cultures),
Respect (valuing others as fellow humans, respecting cultural differences), and
Tolerance (acceptance of diversity and ambiguity),

Mutuality and cultural humility are also listed as essential attitudes that involve being culturally self-aware and valuing others.

The frequently quoted tripartite or ABC model of human behavior is used to describe the skills and characteristics of the intercultural competent: affective, behavioral, and cognitive (Goldstein, 2022b; Hammer, 2015). The list above identified by Deardorff can be categorized accordingly as well: knowledge stands for cognitive, skills for behavioral, and attitudes for affective component.

Pedagogical goals of developing intercultural competence put by J. M. Bennett (2015) – somewhat resonating with the above mentioned competence areas – are curiosity, cognitive flexibility, and non-judgmental attitudes. Curiosity, considered crucial for intercultural competence, enhances other skills. Curious individuals can better explore and interpret cultural differences. Cognitive flexibility, shifting perspectives with empathy, helps reduce prejudice. Lastly, non-judgmentalness enables unbiased learning and fosters cultural humility in interpreting unfamiliar situations. The description-interpretation-evaluation method that helps enhance curiosity, cognitive flexibility, and non-judgmentalness has also been introduced by Bennett (2015).

Several authors have outlined three key steps for effectively interacting and working with individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds. The first step, as consistently highlighted, is cultural self-awareness. In the realm of multicultural counseling, Sue et al. (2019) identify essential competencies for counselors and therapists, which can be viewed as integral to navigating cultural diversity. These competencies include:

- (1) Being aware of one's own assumptions, values, and biases.
- (2) Understanding the worldview of culturally diverse clients.
- (3) Developing appropriate intervention strategies and techniques.

These competencies serve as guiding principles for professionals in multicultural counseling, facilitating culturally sensitive and effective practices.

In a similar vein, Hammer (2015) asserts that intercultural competence entails two primary components: (1) deep self-awareness of one's cultural influences on beliefs, values, and behaviors, and (2) understanding of cultural others and their diverse perspectives. This understanding enables (3) effective navigation of cultural differences.

Cohen-Emerique (2013) proposes a theoretical model and intercultural intervention training program named "culture shock," which outlines three distinct steps aimed at assisting professionals in developing intercultural competence when working

with clients from diverse sociocultural backgrounds. These steps focus on navigating the collision of frames of reference between parties involved:

- (1) Decentralization: Reflecting on oneself to recognize one's own professional, social, and cultural frame of reference. This reflection also extends to clients, encouraging them to evaluate their internalized culture and how it influences their perceptions and participation in interactions.
- (2) Discovering the other's frame of reference, even if one does not agree with it.
- (3) Negotiation and cultural or intercultural mediation, facilitating the convergence of the two frames of reference.

These steps provide a structured approach to understanding and addressing cultural differences, promoting effective communication and collaboration across diverse contexts.

Developmental models

DMIS, the Developmental Model of Intercultural Sensitivity of M. Bennett (1993) identifies various mindsets individuals or groups adopt when encountering cultural differences. Intercultural sensitivity refers to the ability to discriminate, construe, and experience relevant cultural differences. Development is the process when the individuals' experience concerning cultural difference becomes more complex and sophisticated. These mindsets range from ethnocentric to ethnorelative perspectives along a continuum (Figure 5.). The first three ethnocentric stages (placing one's own culture at an absolute central position and avoiding cultural differences) include denial, defense and reversal as well as minimization.

Figure 5. Developmental Model of Intercultural Sensitivity (Bennett & Bennett, 2004)

The denial mindset minimally acknowledges cultural differences, considering one's own culture as the only true culture, showing disinterest and avoidance. Defense and reversal mindsets evaluate differences as "us versus them", with defense

feeling threatened by cultural differences and reversal idealizing other cultures. Minimization transitions between monocultural denial/defense and intercultural acceptance/adaptation, focusing on commonalities but risking superficial understanding. It considers one's own cultural worldview as universal. Despite acknowledging superficial differences, it deems other cultures essentially similar to its own. Hammer (2012) considers Minimization as a stage in-between, it is neither clearly ethnocentric nor clearly ethnorelative.

The following three ethnorelative stages of acceptance, adaptation, and integration involve experiencing one's own culture within the context of other cultures and actively seeking out cultural differences.

Acceptance is about accepting the importance of differences and being curious about differences, even if it does not necessarily mean agreeing with the different worldviews. Adaptation involves cognitive and behavioral shifts to bridge cultural gaps using complex frameworks and adaptive practices. Integration means moving in and out easily of different cultural worldviews, as they become integrated into one's own worldview. Hammer (2012) omitted this stage from the revised model, as he argues that it is not about intercultural sensitivity development, it is rather intercultural, multicultural identity.

Besides Bennett's DMIS model, David Kolb's experiential learning theory (ELT) has also been an influential framework in intercultural competence development. ELT proposes a multi-dimensional approach to human learning. According to this theory, achieving comprehensive learning depends on a learner's ability to engage with four fundamental modes or styles: (1) concrete experience, (2) abstract conceptualization, (3) reflective observation, and (4) active experimentation. Progressing through these modes synergistically is key to holistic learning. However, research with Kolb's Learning Style Inventory (LSI) suggests that most learners do not fully engage with all four modes when left to their own devices. Instead, they tend to rely habitually on one or two learning styles, missing out on the opportunity for comprehensive and holistic learning.

Ng, Van Dyne, & Ang (2009) showed in their investigation that individuals with higher levels of cultural intelligence demonstrate greater capability in actively engaging in the four processes outlined in the Experiential Learning Model.

Main Theoretical models of intercultural competence

A multitude of theoretical models of intercultural competence have emerged. Among the most comprehensive introductions and analyses of these models to date is that provided by Spitzberg and Chagnon (2009). Deardorff's Process Model of Intercultural Competence (Figure 6.) stands out as one of the most renowned and influential theoretical models in the field of intercultural competence within higher education.

Figure 6. Deardorff's Process Model of Intercultural Competence (Spitzberg and Chagnon, 2009)

The model shows the connections between the different individual compositions (attitudes, knowledge, skills) and proposes an interactive process that operates at multiple levels, with feedback loops and sequential causal paths.

Arasaratnam-Smith (2017) warns that in defining intercultural competence, it's crucial to view it holistically, recognizing the involvement of multiple elements beyond individual abilities and characteristics. Interpersonal communication inherently engages the perceptions and skills of multiple parties, influenced by their cultural perspectives and the context of the interaction.

Focus: individual, interactional or embeddedness in a larger context

The many concepts and frameworks of IC could be categorized based on their focus, which is either 1) on the individual level (IC is something in the individual), or 2) on the interaction (IC manifests in intercultural interaction), or 3) on the larger context of intercultural and sociocultural adaptation. The measurements align with the focus.

Deardorff's model, while considered an individual compositional model, is also partially interactional.

The Multicultural Personality Questionnaire (MPQ) by van der Zee and van Oudenhoven (2000), discussed earlier in this review regarding its relevance to personality traits and the adaptation of international students, exemplifies a person-focused approach. Through sample items prompting respondents to rate the extent to which they resemble the described individual, the MPQ effectively taps into intercultural competence:

- cultural empathy („Is attentive to facial expressions“)

- openmindedness („Finds other religions interesting“)
- social initiative („Takes initiatives“)
- emotional stability („Is not easily hurt“)
- flexibility („Easily from one activity to another“)

Another widely applied individual focused framework is Cultural Intelligence by Ang, Van Dyne (2008). Hypothesized as a specific, statelike, individual capacity to adapt effectively to a new cultural, cultural diversity and cross-cultural interaction, it is expected to predict performance and adjustment outcomes in multicultural situations. Similarly to emotional intelligence, it compliments cognitive intelligence. Its four dimensions are comprised of:

Metacognitive CQ involves cultural consciousness and awareness when engaging with individuals from different cultures.

Cognitive CQ encompasses cultural knowledge regarding norms, practices, and conventions across various settings.

Motivational CQ denotes the ability to focus attention and exert effort towards understanding cultural differences.

Behavioral CQ encompasses the range of suitable responses and the ability to display appropriate verbal and non-verbal cues when interacting with those from different cultures.

Although the DMIS model of Milton Bennett has a developmental approach, it is individual-focused.

The AUM Anxiety/Uncertainty Management Theory by Gudykunst (1995) illustrates a clear emphasis on interactional focus. This theory, rooted in Berger and Calabrese's (1975) uncertainty reduction theory (URT), suggests that intercultural encounters, such as interactions with strangers, often evoke feelings of uncertainty and anxiety. Its primary assertion is that successful communication in interpersonal and intergroup settings is directly linked to the management of anxiety and uncertainty. Gudykunst emphasizes that anxiety and uncertainty management serve as fundamental factors for effective communication and play a mediating role in the impact of other variables, such as identities, motivation, and situational processes. In most cases, during communication, people are not fully aware of their behavior; and rather communicate in a mindless manner. The key herefore is mindfulness. Several steps are helpful such as creating new, finer, more specific categories, openness to new information, and acknowledging that others may have a different perspective.

Other theories with a focus on the broader context, such as the cultural learning approach (Masgoret & Ward, 2006) embeds intercultural communication competence within the sociocultural adaptation (how well the acculturating person manages in everyday life).

A decorative circular graphic on the left side of the page, consisting of several colored segments (red, orange, yellow, green, blue, purple) arranged in a ring, partially overlapping the text area.

Recently, emerging ideas suggest that modern societies are becoming so diverse that distinct majority groups are disappearing. Van Oudenhoven and Ward (2013) describe this as a fading majority, making it challenging to define cultural orientation towards either the host society's majority or the cultural group of origin. Thus, the focus shifts from acculturation strategies to individual management of dual or multiple cultural identities. As the number of groups grows, it becomes vital to consider how individuals can personally approach and build relationships with one another (Van Oudenhoven and Benet-Martínez, 2015). In this context, personality-based intercultural competence becomes essential.

Assessment of and tools for developing intercultural competences

More than 100 measures that assess intercultural competence (Deardorff, 2015) have been listed, several systematic reviews and meta-analyses have been conducted on the factors that influence intercultural competence development, different theoretical frameworks of intercultural competence development have been suggested and reviewed (Deardorff, 2015, Deardorff & Arasaratnam-Smith, 2017; Goldstein, 2022b).

In terms of measurements, there are recent reviews, e.g. that of Chen and Gabrenya (2021) on five well-known measures: Sociocultural adaptation scale (1999) of Ward & Kennedy, Cross-cultural adaptation inventory (1995) by Kelley & Meyers; Multicultural personality questionnaire (2000) by Van der Zee & Oudenhoven; Intercultural sensitivity scale (2000) by Chen & Starosta; Cultural intelligence scale (2008) by Ang et al. The Sociocultural Adaptation Scale developed by Ward and Kennedy evaluates intercultural competence while embedding it in a broader context of sociocultural adaptation. It assesses how effectively individuals are navigating and managing their everyday lives within the host context. It has been used widely in works with international students, just as the Multicultural personality questionnaire, Intercultural sensitivity scale, and Cultural intelligence scale. For example, the findings of a survey with 528 international students in Hungary show that higher cultural intelligence (CQ) is associated with better academic adjustment, better psychological well-being, stronger international orientation and stronger local culture orientation, while lower CQ is associated with stronger home orientation, which in turn predicted more negative psychological adaptation (Nguyen Luu, 2019).

Among the five questionnaires mentioned above, the Sociocultural adaptation scale, the Intercultural sensitivity scale, and the Cultural intelligence scale are available for use. There is another scale with good reliability and validity and available, the Intercultural sensitivity inventory developed by Bhawuk and Brislin (1992). This scale evaluates individuals' awareness of behavioral differences based on their engaging with an individualistic or collectivist culture, their receptiveness to cultural differences, and their adaptability to unfamiliar cultural norms.

Large projects and different types of intercultural training tools and activities have been developed over the last decades to enhance intercultural competence. Significant source books with detailed introduction of theoretical background and concepts as well as methodology and often with guides to help reflection are available. Among them are the *IEREST: Intercultural education resources for Erasmus students and their teachers* (2015). *Building Cultural Competence: Innovative Activities and Models* (edited by Berardo & Deardorff, 2012) with more than 50 activities brought by various intercultural trainers from different regions of the world; *52 activities for improving cross-cultural communication* by Stringer and Cassidy (2009); *Education Pack "all different - all equal" - Ideas, resources, methods and activities for non-formal intercultural education with young people and adults* (3rd edition) (2016); *T-Kit 4 Intercultural learning 2nd edition* (Council of Europe, 2018); *Ticket Handbook, Transnational Intercultural Competence through Knowledge Exchange and Training*. Sources can also be found thanks to various Erasmus projects. Among them are materials of Erasmus Mundus (<https://www.em-a.eu/mindful-mundus>), ErasmusSkills (<https://www.erasmuskills.eu/>), SkillMill (www.erasmus-skillmill.com).

Fowler and Yamaguchi (2020) provide an impressive analysis of 18 different intercultural methods with the detailed lists of the strengths and weaknesses of each of them. These are

- cognitive methods (lectures, written materials, online-based training, films, self-assessment, case studies, and critical incidents),
- active methods (role-playing, simulation games, and intercultural exercises),
- intercultural methods (contrast culture training, culture assimilator, cross-cultural analysis, cross-cultural dialogues, areas studies, and immersion),
- other methods (visual imagery and art and culture).

Deardorff (2020) conducted a review of various intercultural training activities and tools. Interpersonal simulations, such as live-action role-playing, offer a platform for honing intercultural skills and behaviors through face-to-face interaction within a controlled environment. Many intercultural tools take the form of group activities, such as role-plays, case studies, and intercultural games. Online tools also fall within her taxonomy. Across all these activity types, critical reflection emerges as a crucial element. Critical reflection involves three dimensions: interpreting one's experiences through descriptive, analytical, and critical lenses; expressing these reflections through mediums like writing, speech, or art; and subsequently taking action informed by the reflection process. One of the frequently used tools is cultural assimilator (for a comprehensive introduction, see Bhawuk, 2017). Culture assimilators are composed of brief scenarios, termed critical incidents, illustrating real-life intercultural encounters between individuals from different cultures. These incidents highlight misunderstandings arising from cultural differences. Following each incident, readers are prompted to reflect on the scenario's source of

misunderstanding through a posed question. They are then presented with four or five possible behavioral responses. Among these options, one reflects the viewpoint of each culture involved, while the others serve as distractors, capturing the confusion experienced by the sojourner. There are critical incidents that are especially tailored for international students (Cushner & Brislin, 1996). In another framework, critical incidents not given by the facilitator, but instead, are collected and told by students and they will be analyzed and reflected for intercultural competence development. A detailed description of the method and sample analysis can be found in the chapter on critical incidents in the book of Lantz-Deaton and Golubeva (2020).

The impact of different intercultural learning programs is measured before and after the intervention. Follow-up or long-term effect measurement also takes place. Bathurst and La Brack (2012) argue that both comparing the post-training with pre-training results as well as comparing between the intercultural level competence of participants and (equivalent) non-participants is important.

An example of comparing pre- and post-intervention findings can be found in the SUCTI (<https://suctiproject.com>) and its later version, SUCTIA project (<https://suctiproject.com/suctia/>). Among others, personality trait (openness) and intercultural competence (using a scale) were measured.

More recently, a specific method, the so-called UNESCO Story Circles method has been introduced in detail (Deardorff, 2020). In UNESCO Story Circles, groups of four to six individuals gather to practice key intercultural skills by authentically sharing their life experiences in response to specific prompts. Deep listening fosters the realization of commonality among participants, nurturing a sense of common humanity through open sharing and learning from each other. Story Circles facilitate the development of intercultural competencies, such as listening for understanding, self-awareness, openness, respect, reflexivity, empathy, and cultural humility.

Inspired by this method, international students share their personal narratives, their lived experiences during their sojourn in a book by Arasatnam-Smith and Deardorff (2022). Via these stories, different crucial aspects of intercultural learning and competence are addressed and reflected. Identity, stereotypes and cultural differences, self-reflection, community support and building deeper relationship by using intercultural competence are the main themes. Readers' self-reflection along these themes is one of the main aims of this method.

Good practices of enhancing intercultural learning of international students: pre-, during, and post-sojourn interventions

In the last decades, a large amount of experience has been accumulated, reported and reflected on regarding intercultural learning-enhancing intervention programs. In one of the previous sections, while discussing the summary of training tools and measurements by Deardorff (2020), we already mentioned some of the good practices (e.g. the story circle method). In the remaining part of the chapter,

we call attention to some of the significant sources of good practices and then will give a subjective list of recommendations. The list we hope will continually grow as the PADMICA team realizes its project, gaining more experiences.

Among significant projects is the IEREST (<http://www.ierest-project.eu/>) that was planned to support the learning process and intercultural competence of students throughout their Erasmus exchange, from the pre-departure phase to their reentry (Beaven & Golubeva, 2016). Different teaching modules were carefully designed based on the experiential learning model by Kolb (see above in the text) and the dynamic, non-essentialist culture concept of Holliday (2013) that mirrors the culture concept of other interventions such as those introduced by Vande Berge and colleagues (2012). This concept argues that an individual engages with numerous diverse cultures, encompassing „large cultures” such as national or ethnic ones and „small cultures” such as being a member of a university class or sport club. The individual might perceive others as „distinct” based on any of the groups to which they belong. These distinctions can arise from factors such as nationality, religion, ethnicity, native language, or even preferences like supporting a different sports team or learning a different language, liking a genre of music and so on. This multifaceted identity adds layers to one's understanding of diversity and belonging. This view is connected to the construct of social identity complexity (Brewer, 2011). The concept of identity and the importance of avoiding identifying others only with their alleged national and ethnic groups is not only a central topic in IEREST, it also serves as a guiding principle.

Ready-to-use theoretical presentation, activities and guidance to help facilitation and reflection are available from IEREST for all the three stages of study abroad: before departure, during study abroad and upon return. .

Vande Berge and colleagues (2012) presented in their seminal book probably the first systematic collection and analysis of different intervention programs and their outcomes. The authors argue for the importance of providing intervention instead of „wishing and waiting” for the positive outcome of intercultural exposure and interaction by itself. Their findings contradicted the "immersion hypothesis," which posited that immersion in a new and different culture would inherently lead to a substantial increase in intercultural competence and awareness. Instead, they argued for the necessity of deliberate, structured interventions to foster such growth. In the 6 different programs introduced in the volume, the Intercultural Development Inventory (IDI) and IDI Guided Development model by Hammer (to lead students from the monocultural mindset to the intercultural one, from the ethnocentric stage to the ethnorelative one) was used. Detailed introduction of each intervention program is to be found in the book with recommendations for planning similar projects. IDI is a paying tool that can be used only by qualified facilitators who obtained training from the authors and owners of the tool.

Jackson and Oguro (2018) give a more recent collection of good practices in intercultural competence trainings for study abroad students. They argue that the development of intercultural competence is an ongoing journey that extends beyond the study abroad experience and persists even after students return home. Their theoretical underpinnings are similar to those of IEREST (IEREST was presented in a chapter of their book also) and they argue against the essentializing of culture, and call attention to the importance of addressing identity questions and avoiding stereotyping and „othering”. Several easy-to-use tools are referred to,

or mentioned in the volume. Among them is this online source with a specific method that could be used as a qualitative measurement for participants to follow their development from before to after the training: Autobiography of Intercultural Encounters - Autobiography of Intercultural Encounters (coe.int). It's a theoretically based self-assessment tool. The results could be reflected in pairs or small groups.

Other authors, by summarizing the literature, pointed out important information that can be used in planning preparation and debriefing programs. Sit and Mak (2017) build on the ABC (affective, behavioral, cognitive) model of acculturation by Ward (2001). After analyzing more than 30 cross-cultural training programs, they suggest that programs incorporating behavioral elements (practicing appropriate behaviors for cross-cultural interactions) demonstrated the most consistent effectiveness. Those combining both behavioral and cognitive components (the latter addresses maladaptive communication patterns and cultural sensitivity) proved more effective compared to programs focusing solely on cognitive aspects or didactic methods (the latter means psychoeducation, geopolitical information, and practical advice).

Others (Pilon, 2017; Williams, 2009) provide full-text tools for the good practice of reflection, an element that has an important in all training programs, with no exception. Students should get the opportunity to discuss their learning, engage in reflective writing, and explore applications of new knowledge beyond the classroom. It is recommended that reflection should be seamlessly integrated throughout the entire program, encompassing pre-departure, during the overseas experience, and upon reentry. Critical, good quality reflection is needed as well as professional facilitation. To achieve this aim, the staff has to be previously trained. Besides the long list of critical reflection exercises, Pilon gives specific advices in the study. These are as follows:

- Aligning reflection activities with the planned learning outcomes. Similarly to other good practices, the planning of learning outcomes should take place at the beginning of all interventions, after learning about the specific characteristics and needs of the trainees on individual and group level.
- Intervening consistently throughout the study abroad cycle: before, during, and after. Offering pre-departure activities for anticipatory learning, facilitating group discussions and journaling abroad for real-time reflection, and providing re-entry programming for reflective learning.
- Offering various reflection methods: written tasks, individual and collaborative creative projects, and both small- and large-group discussions led by students and faculty.
- Establishing assessment criteria for these outcomes and adjust the program accordingly based on assessment findings.

The present chapter reviewed the rich literature on theoretical concepts as well as measurements and developing tools and good practices of intercultural preparations and post-mobility programs. Drawing on this valuable knowledge base, we will compile a list of recommendations

The present chapter has extensively reviewed the literature on theoretical concepts, measurement tools, methods, and best practices regarding intercultural interventions for international students. Drawing on this valuable knowledge base, in the next chapter, we will compile a list of recommendations for our PADMICA project.

Recommendations for designing and implementing intercultural intervention programs

In the next part, we attempt to give an overview of the recommendations based on literature review that could be considered for the pre-mobility preparation and post-mobility debriefing modules.

Some general ideas to keep in mind throughout the programs

- Considering intercultural learning as a long-life process. Everyone has some experiences already. There is a basis to build on.
- Nothing is as practical as a good theory.
- Acknowledging that there is no universally superior method to intervene effectively, while intervention is needed (and it's essential to keep looking for good practices).

The start: planning the „what“

Figure 7. Factors affecting content and method selection. Fowler & Yamaguchi (2020)

- Careful planning and selecting the intervention methods, taking into account several factors, conditions (see Figure 7.).
- Knowing the characteristics and needs of students.
- Setting realistic learning outcomes for the program and design it accordingly.
- Considering the entire circle from pre-mobility to post-mobility. While planning for pre-mobility preparation, take into account the planned goals of post-mobility program.
- Developing and implementing an effective assessment program utilizing valid, reliable (and of course, feasible, available) instruments and rigorous methodologies.
- Letting participants know that this is a culture-general program. Host country-specific information has to be given in another framework, or activities can be organized when students try to get and shared information about host country and university (outside training time, could be homework assignment).

The „who”

The trainer and facilitator

- Paying due attention to the (well-prepared) trainers and facilitators' crucial role. They are the key not only in implementing the intervention program but also in helping critical reflections of students.
- Training trainers and facilitators in the theory and practice of intercultural learning.
- Understanding the process of acculturation and adaptation of international students as background knowledge will be practical during the intervention programs.
- Expanding your toolkit by familiarizing yourself with various methods, enabling flexibility in their application based on situational needs.

The student

- We mentioned about the keyrole of trainers/facilitators, still the program should be learner-centered, the students control their learning and reflection (and can be co-facilitator for other participants). Faciliator steps in when needed.
- Involving international students and returning students, building on their experiences and perspectives.
- Returning students can take part (and reflect on and share experiences) in a preparation program as experienced experts and at the same time, this can be a part of the debriefing.

Some more thoughts on the „how”

- Facilitating, guiding, and putting the learner in charge in the appropriate time are keys to success
- Helping students cultivate self-reflection as cultural individuals and become aware of their typical responses and interpretations within diverse cultural settings
- Online and offline methods, combination of the two (e.g. reflections can go well online).
- Incorporating gamification, visualizations, and other online applications to appeal to this generation of students.
- Take participants to the field to practice intercultural interactions, skills. E.g. bring them together with international students on campus.
- Making direct connections between activities and desired learning outcomes (make the participants talk about this).
- Connecting the pre-departure and post-sojourn training content.
- Considering practicalities: the ways to get students to participate (especially after mobility).

Concluding thoughts

The aim of this review is to establish the theoretical and practical foundation of the PADMICA project by drawing on existing literature in the field. Based on the literature, we argued for the necessity of deliberate and planned development of intercultural competence and the critical, guided reflection on experiences gained during study abroad. Facilitating this requires an understanding of the processes students undergo while abroad and after return, the acculturation and adaptation processes that occur, and the factors influencing the success of their mobility in psychological, sociocultural, academic, and intercultural domains. From the rich literature on intercultural competence, definitions, categorization of its components, theoretical models, including theoretical frameworks for the development of intercultural competence, measurement and development tools, as well as some good practices, are presented. Finally, building on the literature, we began to list the considerations that could be used for the pre-mobility preparation and post-mobility debriefing modules of our PADMICA project. With hopes that the list will grow with the project's progression and experiences, PADMICA aims to contribute to the advancement of the field.

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